

A Study on Physical Facilities Provided in Primary Schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

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Abstract: *The study focused on the provision of physical facilities in primary schools and to provide relevant suggestions. Total 192 schools 8 schools from each district, 4 male and 4 female- 2 from urban and 2 from rural area were included in the study. An observation Performa regarding physical facilities provided in the schools was used as an instrument for the collection of relevant data. For the purpose of data analysis, percentage was used. The result shows that majority of the schools have insufficient rooms. Teaching is carried out in rooms where available.*

Key Words: Study, Physical Facilities, Primary Schools

Introduction

Regarding human capital model, economic growth shows that increase/growth in the level of education brings increase/growth in the field of education. Educated people play a vital role every field; they think up new and better forms of production; and they can bring positive changes in each and every field of life and quickly learn new skills. So, the existence of such productive and skilled persons is only possible when there is a system of compulsory primary education.

[Garneir and Stain \(2018\)](#) Better literacy and elementary education help every person to understand their needs and demand services and permits an individual to progress the knowledge and services to imprisonment economic chances and thus in this way they can increase his or her income. This thing provides opportunities to individuals to learn more and deliver more. For their families educated men can take better decisions shown in the research studies. Education increases facilities for society and at the same time advance the consumption of these services ([Young, Oetting & Defenbacher, 2016](#)).

[McGinn et al \(2019\)](#) Education is a very important tool for us to struggle for economic development. We educate ourselves because of our dreams and goals in life. Doctors, engineers and nurses many other professions are possible because of educators. Educators transmit information to learners they are responsible for the teaching learning- process.

Understanding teaching starts from developing of able concept of teaching that goes beyond analyzing teaching mythology and describing the various activities that go into the process. For that matter educators, in particular, realized the need for investigating facet of teaching with the end because of improving it. Such a process requires acknowledgement of what has to be improved by thorough analyses of records of action in a classroom situation ([McMillan, 2018](#)).

The schools actually have to function as an integral aspect of each community. Cooperation and coordination with other agencies of government in many communities this coordination have been maintained on a voluntary base. Its operation is a democracy that is very desirable. Leadership always requires cooperation and coordination but not a dictatorship. ([Morphet, 2017](#)).

Problem Statement

Problem under investigation was “A study on physical facilities provided in primary schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa”.

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Research Objectives

Following are the main objectives of the study:

1. To know about the existing condition of schools regarding physical facilities.
2. Make suggestions for physical facilities where necessary.

Significance of the Study

In Pakistan, there is an increasing concern with both quality and access to primary education for all. In rural and urban female primary schools in D.I. Khan District. It highlights the management practices and administrative problems of head teachers which can result in improved performance in national examinations in the district. The study will provide a part of valid and reliable knowledge, which could be used, for further improvement in Primary education.

Limitations / Delimitations

The study was undertaken subject to the following limitations and delimitations.

1. Only eight schools four for boys and four for girls, two from either area of urban/rural could be included from each district.
2. Sample of one hundred and ninety two schools was considered as sufficient representations of all the population.
3. The interview schedule for teachers was considered as the only suitable data gathering instrument.
4. Data for five years (2016-2020) was considered as sufficient to indicate trends in gross and net attendance and dropout.

Research Methodology

Population

All the government primary schools in KP formed the population of the study. There are 22466 schools for boys and girls in urban and rural areas of KP as per statistics of EMIS (2007).

Sample

Sample of eight schools, four male (two rural and two urban) and four female (two rural and two urban) was drawn from each district. Thus a total sample of one hundred and ninety two schools was selected randomly from all the twenty six districts. A comprehensive list of schools for each of the above districts was obtained from Director Schools and literacy Peshawar. Keeping in view the aims and objectives of the study urban, rural, male and female schools were equally represented in the sample.

Instrument

An observation Performa regarding physical facilities provided in the schools was prepared by the researcher and the experts of IER Gomal University. Observation perform was comprised of twenty three items. A research team was prepared to visit the schools and collect data regarding physical facilities.

Procedure

The above stated tools were field-tested in twenty urban-rural and male-female schools. The purpose of field testing was to improve the instruments and procedure for data collection and to get a clear picture of difficulties and field experiences. In the light of the field testing, the instruments were modified accordingly.

Just after validation of research instruments, data was collected. Research team actively participated in this gigantic task of national importance. In some cases and some districts it took much time due to the worst situation of law and order. Members of research team visited the selected schools and physically

checked the data regarding the school statistics and the absence or presence of the physical facilities was checked on the spot.

Statistical analysis

Collected data were analyzed with the help of tables. Comparisons were made with the help of percentages.

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Table 1. Showing number of rooms

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
None	4	1	3	1	9	4.6875
Enough	19	18	21	22	80	41.6666667
Insufficient	25	29	24	25	103	53.6458333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 1 shows that 53.64% and 41.66% of schools have insufficient and enough rooms respectively whereas 4.68% of schools are running without this facility. A great number of rural boy's schools followed by urban boys and rural girl's schools have insufficient rooms in proportion to its classes.

Table 2. Showing nature of teaching learning place

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Room	35	31	32	29	127	66.1458333
Veranda	7	10	10	14	41	21.3541667
Open Space	6	7	6	5	24	12.5
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 2 shows that 66% of schools have rooms, 21% have verandas and 13% use open space for teaching learning. The proportion of boys' schools followed by girls' schools in urban areas is greater than the other schools in having rooms for teaching learning. A bigger number of rural girls' schools use verandas. Open space is used by almost an equal number of all the schools.

Table 3. Showing number of classes in a single room

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
One	33	18	22	16	89	46.3541667
Two	10	22	20	20	72	37.5
More than Two	5	8	6	12	31	16.1458333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 3 shows that 46.35% of schools have room for every class against 37.5% where two classes are adjusted in a single room. There are more than two classes in a single room in 16.14% of schools. Urban boys' schools have, in a great number a room for each class against great number of rural girls' schools where more than two classes are adjusted in a single room.

Table 4. Showing structure of classroom

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Good	17	14	11	11	53	27.6041667

Satisfactory	17	20	26	28	91	47.3958333
Un satisfactory	14	14	11	9	48	25
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 4 shows that 47.39% of schools have a satisfactory structure of classroom against 27.6% where structure is good. 25% of schools have an unsatisfactory structure in their classrooms. Girls' schools have their classrooms with a satisfactory structure in a greater proportion than the boys' schools. Great number of boy's schools gets their classroom in unsatisfactory condition than the girls' schools in the relevant category of unsatisfactory structure.

Table 5. Showing classroom size

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Appropriate To Some Extent	21	22	19	18	80	41.6666667
In appropriate	17	16	18	22	73	38.0208333
Total	10	10	11	8	39	20.3125
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 5 shows that 41.66% followed by 38% of schools have appropriate and to some extent appropriate classroom size in accordance with their student's strength. Whereas, 20.31% have classrooms with inappropriate size. There is almost same variation across these categories.

Table 6. Showing nature of seats

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Tat	31	37	31	35	134	69.7916667
Bench	13	11	13	12	49	25.5208333
Chair	4	0	4	1	9	4.6875
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 6 shows that 69.79% of schools use jute tats for their students to sit on against 25.52% where benches are available for sitting purpose. 4.68% of schools have chairs for their students. Majority of rural schools use jute tats than urban ones whereas majority of urban schools use benches and chairs than the rural ones.

Table 7. Showing availability of seats

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Fully	18	14	17	19	68	35.4166667
Partially	14	13	21	18	66	34.375
Not Enough	16	21	10	11	58	30.2083333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 7 shows that 35.4% followed by 34.3% of schools are fully and partially equipped with seating against 30.2% where seating is found as not enough. Girls' schools are comparatively more equipped with seating facilities than boys' schools. Rural boys' schools exceed others in not having this facility as enough in accordance with student's strength.

Table 8. Showing condition of available seats

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Good	13	13	12	17	55	28.6458333
Satisfactory	22	19	29	22	92	47.9166667
Un Satisfactory	13	16	7	9	45	23.4375
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 8 shows that 47.91% of schools have satisfactory seating against 28.64% where condition of such seating is good. There are 23.43% of schools where seating condition is unsatisfactory. Girl's schools are in a better position in having good and satisfactory seating for students.

Table 9. Showing electrification

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	30	29	32	20	111	57.8125
Existed but unsatisfactory	11	6	7	17	41	21.3541667
Not Existed	7	13	9	11	40	20.8333333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 9 shows that 57.81% of schools are electrified against 21.35% where the facility exists but in unsatisfactory condition. 20.83% of schools run without being electrified. Urban schools are in a better position to have this facility. Rural girl's schools are electrified but in an unsatisfactory way. Greater number is found for rural schools where this facility is nonexistent.

Table 10. Showing availability of bulbs and fans

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	27	24	28	18	97	50.5208333
Existed but unsatisfactory	15	8	12	17	52	27.0833333
Not Existed	6	16	8	13	43	22.3958333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 10 shows that 50.52% of schools enjoy the facility of bulbs and fans against 27% of schools where this facility exists to an unsatisfactory level. Still 22.39% of schools run without having this facility. Rural schools constitute greater portion of not existed category. Urban schools are found in greater number where this facility is available.

Table 11. Showing availability of day light

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	32	33	31	30	126	65.625
Existed but unsatisfactory	14	6	12	12	44	22.9166667
Not Existed	2	9	5	6	22	11.4583333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 11 shows that 65.62% of schools are fully exposed to day light whereas 22.91% do have this facility but in unsatisfactory nature. There is no variation among the schools where the facility is fully available. Rural boys' schools lag behind the others in having this facility but in unsatisfactory condition.

Table 12. Showing availability of air

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	36	36	31	37	140	72.9166667
Existed but unsatisfactory	11	7	14	9	41	21.3541667
Not Existed	1	5	3	2	11	5.72916667
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 12 shows that 72.91% of schools are well ventilated against 21.35% where air exists in unsatisfactory form. Urban girls' schools lag behind the others in having this facility and in having it in unsatisfactory form.

Table 13. Showing availability of toilets

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	24	25	22	19	90	46.875
Existed but unsatisfactory	14	9	21	21	65	33.8541667
Not Existed	10	14	5	8	37	19.2708333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 13 reveals that 46.87% of schools run with having this facility against 33.85% where this facility exists in unsatisfactory form 19.27% of schools have no wash rooms. Urban boys' schools are in greater number, enjoying this facility against greater number of girl's schools where this facility is found in unsatisfactory condition as is shown by the bar graph.

Table 14. Showing white wash/paints

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	30	30	26	27	113	58.8541667
Existed but unsatisfactory	13	15	19	15	62	32.2916667
Not Existed	5	3	3	6	17	8.85416667
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 14 shows that 58.85% of schools are well white washed/painted against 32.29% in an unsatisfactory form. Boy's schools are in greater number, white washed than girls' schools. Urban girls' schools exceed the other in having this facility in an unsatisfactory form.

Table 15. Showing availability of writing board

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	32	36	31	28	127	66.1458333
Existed but unsatisfactory	13	9	16	17	55	28.6458333
Not Existed	3	3	1	3	10	5.20833333

Total	48	48	48	48	192	100
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Table 15 shows that 66% schools have writing boards in a good condition against 28.64% schools where condition of writing boards is not satisfactory. Rural boy's schools exceed others in having this facility in good form girl's schools are found in greater number where this facility exists in unsatisfactory condition.

Table 16. Showing availability of teaching staff

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	30	27	39	27	123	64.0625
Existed but unsatisfactory	12	14	8	18	52	27.0833333
Not Existed	6	7	1	3	17	8.85416667
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 16 shows that 64% schools are well staffed according to the number of classes against 27% schools understaffed. Urban girl's schools are in greater proportion, well-staffed than the others against rural girl's schools in which greater proportion is found understaffed. Rural boy's schools are comparatively more understaffed.

Table 17. Showing boundary wall

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	33	28	39	29	129	67.1875
Existed but unsatisfactory	10	10	8	13	41	21.3541667
Not Existed	5	10	1	6	22	11.4583333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 17 shows that 67.18% schools are well surrounded by boundary walls against 21.35% schools having unsatisfactory condition of boundary walls. Girl's schools are in good position than boys schools in having boundary wall facility. Rural boy's schools are in comparatively more deprived of having this facility than the others.

Table 18. Showing classroom cleanliness

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	28	33	35	29	125	65.1041667
Existed but unsatisfactory	17	8	12	14	51	26.5625
Not Existed	3	7	1	5	16	8.3333333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 18 shows that 65% classrooms are cleaned against 8.33% where cleanliness condition is unsatisfactory. Urban girl's classrooms are more cleaned than rural ones. Rural boy's schools lack this aspect more the others.

Table 19. Showing availability of windows/ventilators

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	31	37	37	29	134	69.7916667

Existed but unsatisfactory	12	7	9	15	43	22.3958333
Not Existed	5	4	2	4	15	7.8125
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 19 shows that 69.79% schools have this facility against 22.39% where the condition of windows/ventilators is unsatisfactory. Rural boy's and urban girl's schools enjoy this facility in great number than the others. Rural girl's and urban boy's schools are, in great number, in a state of unsatisfactory than rural boys and urban girls.

Table 20. Showing school cleanliness

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	32	36	35	30	133	69.2708333
Existed but unsatisfactory	14	7	11	10	42	21.875
Not Existed	2	5	2	8	17	8.85416667
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 20 shows that 69% schools are cleaned against 21.87% where the state of cleanliness is found as unsatisfactory. Rural boy's schools and urban girl's schools are more cleaned than the others. Rural girl's schools are found dirtier than the others.

Table 21. Showing availability of lawns and plants

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	22	18	14	19	73	38.0208333
Existed but unsatisfactory	11	10	16	10	47	24.4791667
Not Existed	15	19	18	19	71	36.9791667
Total	48	47	48	48	191	99.4791667

Table 21 shows that 38% schools have lawns and plants against 36.97% where lawns and plants are nonexistent. Urban boys have this facility in greater number than the girls.

Table 22. Showing availability of AV aids in classroom

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	13	22	22	17	74	38.5416667
Existed but unsatisfactory	25	12	14	12	63	32.8125
Not Existed	10	14	12	19	55	28.6458333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 22 shows that 38.54% schools have AV aids in classroom against 32.8% where condition of such material is found unsatisfactory. 28.64% schools have no AV aids at all. Rural boy's and urban girl's schools share in number where the facility is focused in greater number. Urban rural schools are Proportionally more where the state of this facility is unsatisfactory. Rural girls are in greater number deprived of this facility.

Table 23. Showing display of charts/writing on walls

Responses	Urban Males	Rural Males	Urban Females	Rural Females	Total	Percentage
Existed	20	27	27	20	94	48.9583333
Existed but unsatisfactory	14	13	14	14	55	28.6458333
Not Existed	14	8	7	14	43	22.3958333
Total	48	48	48	48	192	100

Table 23 shows that 48.95% classrooms are founded to be decorated with charts hanging on the walls and some slogans are written on it against 28.64% classrooms where this condition is unsatisfactory. 22.39% classrooms have no writing/charts on the walls. Rural boys and urban girls equally share this condition in greater number where walls are decorated against equal number across the categories where decoration of walls is in unsatisfactory state.

Research Findings

Following were the research findings

1. 54% primary schools have insufficient accommodation followed by 42% where enough rooms are found in accordance to number of classes. (see table 1.2.1)
2. Rooms are used for teaching learning purposes in 66% schools. There is still 12% shelter-less schools where education is imparted to the children. (see table 1.2.2)
3. One class is found in one room in 46% schools and two classes in a single room in 37% schools. Urban boy's schools are in a better position of having separate room for each class than the others. (see table 1.2.3)
4. Condition of structure of classroom is satisfactory in 47% schools but unsatisfactory in 25% schools. Girls' schools are in a better position in having satisfactory condition of the building against boys' schools where mixed situation is found. (see table 1.2.4)
5. 20% schools are found having inappropriate size of classroom in proportion to the number of students against 80% schools where students found appropriate or to some extent appropriate space used for seating arrangements. 5% urban schools are provided with chairs for the students. (see table 1.2.6)
6. 35% are fully and 34% are partially equipped with seating while 30% schools have not enough facility for seating while 30% schools have not enough facility for seating of students. Boys are in great number deprived of this facility than girls. (see table 1.2.7)
7. The condition of available in the class. (see table 1.2.5)
8. 70% schools have jute tats seating is found satisfactory in 48% schools and very good in 29% schools. However, 23% schools are in an unsatisfactory position. Girls' schools are relatively in a better position than boys. (see table 1.2.8)
9. 58% schools are found electrified. Conditions of 21% schools are not satisfactory. Still 21% schools are deprived of this facility. Rural schools are comparatively more deprived than urban ones. (see table 1.2.9)
10. 51% schools are provided with the bulbs and fans. 27% schools do have this facility but in an unsatisfactory condition. 22% schools are functioning without this facility. Rural schools are comparatively less facilitated than urban ones. (see table 1.2.10)
11. 66% schools are fully exposed to daylight against 23% where situation of light is not so good. Almost no gender and location wise variation is found in all the schools where daylight exists. (see table 1.2.11)
12. 73% schools are found airy. Only 6% schools are structurally so designed where cross ventilation is not operative. (see table 1.2.12)
13. Washrooms are available to 47% schools. 34% schools have this facility but with unsatisfactory conditions. Girls' schools are comparatively more facilitated than boys. (see table 1.2.13)

14. 59% schools are painted / white washed. Further, 32% schools were found with unsatisfactory condition on this aspect. Almost one and the same situation is found across the categories. (see table 1.2.14)
15. 66% schools got writing boards. Black boards were found with unsatisfactory condition in 29% schools. Boys schools are in improved conditions on this aspect than girls. (see table 1.2.15)
16. There is no problem of availability of staff to 64% schools. However, 27% schools are not staffed adequately. 9% schools are functioning without teachers. Girls' schools in urban area are in a better position than all others. (see table 1.2.16)
17. 67% schools are surrounded by boundary walls. This condition is found unsatisfactory for 21% schools. Still, 1% schools are left without boundary walls. Urban schools are well protected than rural ones. (see table 1.2.17)
18. 65% classrooms are found in a neat and clean form. Cleanliness condition is unsatisfactory in 27% classrooms. The condition is found better in urban areas. (see table 1.2.18)
19. Windows and ventilators are found in 70% schools. The situation is better in rural boys and urban girls' schools. (see table 1.2.19)
20. 69% schools are found in a cleaned form. 9% schools are worse on this aspect. Rural girls lag behind all others in cleanliness. (see table 1.2.20)
21. Lawns are available to and plants are planted in 38% schools. 37% schools are without lawns and plants. Situation is only better in urban boys' schools. (see table 1.2.21)
22. A.V. aids are available to 39% schools. 33% schools have this facility in unsatisfactory condition. 29% schools are deprived of having illustrative materials. Rural girls' schools are comparatively in the worst position. (see table 1.2.22)
23. 49% schools are found to have charts displayed and where slogans are written on walls. 22% schools have no charts/ writing on walls. Rural boys and urban girls' school seem better than their respective counterparts. (See table 1.2.23)

Research Conclusions

1. Majority of the schools have insufficient rooms. Teaching is carried out in rooms where available.
2. Majority got no problem of structure of classroom, classroom size, electrification, availability of bulbs and fans, daylight, air, washrooms, white wash of building, writing board, teaching staff, boundary walls, windows and ventilators, cleanliness of classrooms and school. However, they face problems of availability of seats, its nature and condition, plants and lawns and AV aids.

Recommendations

1. Physical facilities contribute towards the improvement of learning. Schools running with insufficient facilities need to be surveyed and equipped with the necessary equipment.
2. Further studies involving a bigger sample need to be conducted to highlight aspects not covered by this study.

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